

From The Desk of Guest Editor....

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Dentistry which came to almost a standstill due to sudden outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic two years back has bounced back with new energy which is being reflected in new products specially tailor made for clinical & research oriented Dentistry.

It is just amazing how technology is changing the future of dentistry. Online communication tools provide professionals the opportunity to monitor their patient's treatment progress and address any questions at an early stage. Newer technologies from virtual reality through Artificial Intelligence (A.I.) to Microscopic Dentistry will revolutionize dentistry and our whole attitude towards oral health in the future.

Artificial Intelligence - Already dentists employ software to get insights into clinical decision making. These will develop further to integrate A.I. algorithms to enable clinicians to find the best modalities for their patients.

Smart toothbrush - Our home will be filled with connected, smart devices in the

future, so why would our bathroom be an exception. At first, it might feel a bit strange to let a sensor into one of your most intimate activities, tooth brushing, but it makes a lot easier to maintain oral hygiene and prevent plaque or cavities.

Augmented Reality - You might be familiar with Augmented Reality (AR) through social media apps; it's the same technology that Snapchat uses to superimpose filters on your face during your guilt trip selfie with a dog face filter. But AR also found a home in dentistry for both educational and clinical purposes.

Virtual Reality in Dentistry - By slipping such a headset on their head, students and aspiring dental surgeons can be transported to the Operating room from their couch; while patients can visualize a calming landscape while seated at the dreaded dentist's chair to improve their experience. Today only a few students can peek over the shoulder of the surgeon during an operation and it is challenging to learn the tricks of the trade like that. With a virtual reality camera surgeons can stream operations globally and allow dental students to actually be there in the Operatory room using their VR goggles.

Teledentistry - If we as dentist are reluctant to go to a fellow dentist for a treatment due to fear & lack of time, imagine how hard it is for children & patients with special needs or the elderly in nursing homes to have an easy and comfortable access. Another issue is distance. People living in rural areas rarely get access to a dentist and almost never have the possibility of choice. This can change significantly with the spread of teledentistry.

Computer- Assisted design and 3D-printing - 3D-printing does not need any introduction considering the buzz it generated in healthcare a while ago with the technology's potential to print prosthetics and even organ replicas.

Regenerative dentistry - We have come to expect to have our teeth fall off with age or with damage and have them replaced by prosthesis. However the field of regenerative dentistry challenges this preconceived idea with developments that can lead to self-healing teeth and biological therapy for damaged teeth.

Microscopic Dentistry- Magnification has completely changed the finesse of clinical work. It has also taught us a lot about ergonomics.

So it's research oriented clinical Dentistry and it's booming and it's just the tip of the iceberg. So let's enjoy the advancements and slowly implement it in our day to day clinical practice .

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